

Measurements and TCAD simulations of guard-ring structures of thin silicon sensors before and after irradiation

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ABSTRACT

The developing of high performing silicon detectors for particle tracking in the next generation of high-energy physics experiments at future colliders (e.g., HL-LHC, FCC) able to operate efficiently up to very high fluence ($\sim 1 \cdot 10^{17}$ $1 \text{ MeV n}_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$) is of the utmost importance. In order to sustain high voltage values with minimum leakage current injection into the core region of the sensor, the design and optimisation of the Guard-Ring (GR) protection structure is crucial, especially when small substrate thicknesses are used. In a recent R&D batch produced at Fondazione Bruno Kessler (FBK) in the framework of the “eXFlu” project - INFN CSN5 grant for Young Researchers, different optimisation studies of GR structures for thin substrates (45, 30, 20 and 15 μm) up to high fluence ($2.5 \cdot 10^{15}$ $1 \text{ MeV n}_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$) have been addressed. These have been enabled thanks to ad-hoc advanced Technology CAD (TCAD) modelling of different GR design strategies, accounting for the comprehensive bulk and surface radiation-induced damage effects, and an extensive test campaign on such GR structures, both before and after irradiation. In this paper the validation of the development framework of the various GR design options before and after irradiation is presented.

1. Introduction

The next generation of High Energy Physics (HEP) experiments at future hadronic colliders (e.g., FCC-hh) will require tracking detectors to operate efficiently up to very high fluence ($\sim 1 \cdot 10^{17}$ $1 \text{ MeV n}_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$) [1]. The design of the Guard-Ring (GR) protection structure is crucial to obtain high performing silicon detectors able to sustain high voltage values with minimum leakage current injection into the core region, especially when small substrate thicknesses are used.

In a recent R&D batch produced at Fondazione Bruno Kessler (FBK) in the framework of the INFN CSN5 “eXFlu” research project, different optimisation studies of GR structures for thin substrates (ranging from 15 μm to 45 μm) operating at high fluence have been addressed. These studies have been enabled by Technology CAD (TCAD) simulations of GR structures, accounting for both different design strategies, e.g., zero-guard and multi-guard structures, extension of the periphery region, as

well as the comprehensive bulk and surface damage effects induced by radiation on silicon sensors. To validate the development framework, an extensive test campaign has been performed on these GR structures, both before and after irradiation (up to $\sim 2.5 \cdot 10^{15}$ $1 \text{ MeV n}_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$). This involves an analysis of the agreement between simulated and experimental data obtained from the various GR design options, which is presented in this paper.

2. Devices under test, experimental setup and method

The Devices Under Test (DUT) considered for this study were p-n sensors coming from the first R&D batch of the “eXFlu” project produced at FBK and called “EXFLU1”. They are characterised by different thicknesses (45, 30, 20 and 15 μm) of high-resistivity epitaxial

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Fig. 1. Layout of a GR protection structure implemented in 2D domain.

layer, and by GR strategies which were designed and produced in sixteen different designs (S1–S16). These designs differ in the number of floating GRs (zero, one or three) that use one or both of n-deep and p-stop implants, their position between the Bias Ring (BR) and the scribbleline, extension of the metal overhangs and of the overall periphery region. Details about the I–V setup can be found in [2].

3. Simulation findings and model validation

The layouts of the different GR protection structures were implemented in 2D domain by using the state-of-the-art TCAD suite of tools (Fig. 1). The epitaxial thickness and doping concentration values were extracted from capacitance–voltage measurements of the real sensors and fed into the TCAD simulations. The radiation damage effects were modelled by means of the “Perugia Modified Doping” TCAD radiation damage model [3]. This numerical model makes use of two acceptors and one donor deep-level radiation-induced traps coupled with the fluence-dependent analytical parameterisation (called “Torino parameterisation” [2]) to account not only for the combined bulk and surface radiation damage effects, but also for the saturation of the acceptor-creation mechanism in the epitaxial. This recent release of the Perugia radiation damage model was already validated by comparing simulations and measurements of different types of silicon sensors (p-i-n and LGAD) coming from production runs of different vendors [4,5].

To have a direct comparison with the experimental data, the simulations were performed in the same measurement conditions (i.e., temperature and irradiation level). The I–V curves of the GR structures before irradiation were simulated at 298 K, instead the ones after irradiation were simulated at 248 K and then scaled to 273 K to consider the temperature dependence of the current generated in the silicon bulk. The Massey avalanche model [6] was used by extending the TCAD “portfolio” through the code library customisation. Fig. 2 shows the comparison among the experimental and simulated curves related to the 20 μm -thick S2 GR design before and after irradiation. A good match was obtained in terms of V_{BD} and increase of I_{leak} as the fluence (Φ) increases, and similar results were obtained for the other GR design strategies.

4. Conclusions

In this paper the validation of a TCAD model for the numerical simulation of Guard-Ring (GR) protection structures has been presented. Relying on a physics-based approach, the “Perugia Modified Doping”

Fig. 2. Simulated and measured I–V curves of the 20 μm -thick S2 GR design, before irradiation (298 K) and after irradiation ($1.5 \cdot 10^{15} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$, 273 K). The shaded green bands of the experimental data indicate the variability observed by measuring different samples of the S2 GR design in the same conditions. As expected, the increase of the fluence lead to the increase of the leakage current and the breakdown voltage.

radiation damage model has been used for the simulation of such structures after irradiation. An extensive test campaign on different GR design options coming from the “EXFLU1” R&D batch of the FBK technology, both before and after irradiation, has been carried out. The I–V characteristics and breakdown voltages of the 20 μm -thick S2 GR design before and after irradiation have been well reproduced in simulation, as well as the ones of the other GR design strategies. This confirms the high-predictive power of the developed TCAD model, fostering its adoption in the design and optimisation of the future productions of thin silicon sensors (e.g., p-i-n, LGAD) for high fluence applications.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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